

WHITE PAPER ON RESEARCH IT COMPETENCY

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1. What is Research IT?

Research IT refers to the specialised field of information technology that supports and enhances research activities. It encompasses a wide range of services, tools, and infrastructure designed to facilitate the collection, management, analysis, and dissemination of research and research data. Key components of Research IT include high-performance computing (HPC), data storage solutions, software development for research applications, cybersecurity and compliance for research data, and collaborative platforms for researchers.

Research IT is a core function in HEIs for a variety of reasons:

- Enhanced Research Capabilities
- Effective Data Management
- Improved collaboration
- Security
- Compliance
- Resource optimisation
- Training

In contrast to central IT services, Research IT has a more specialised focus, with more requirements in advanced computing and research-specific tools. Research IT is generally responsible for the development and support of specialised infrastructure(s), and allocation of resources, rather than broad use, centrally procured system support. With technological advances, there is now an increased emphasis on security, in particular data security, and compliance across a range of research-specific ethical and legal requirements. Finally, there is often an increased training requirement.

2. Research IT as a University Function

As described, Research IT is specialised and focused on supporting research activities: it is a set of services and support provided to the research community by the institution.

2.1 Core Technical Competences

While several models are available and not every institution supports all these services; in general, Research IT provides and supports many of the following services:

- **Advanced Computing:** Many research projects require significant computational power. Research IT provides access to supercomputers, clusters, and cloud resources for complex simulations, modelling, and data analysis. Linux servers play a crucial role in research computing.
- **Data Storage Solutions:** Research IT offers access to data storage options to support researchers throughout their work, including network drives, cloud storage, high performance filesystems, dedicated research data storage repositories, 'configure and compute' systems. They ensure security, preservation, and compliance with data management protocols. Additionally, Research IT may assist researchers in effectively managing and sharing their data, e.g., via secure file transfer such as HEAnet's Filesender.

- **Data Centre Hosting:** Hosting research equipment in on-campus data centres.
- **Software Set Up & Troubleshooting:** Research IT personnel can help troubleshoot issues, including research software installation, hardware malfunctions, data storage and backup, security concerns, user account problems, and performance optimisation, e.g. bioinformatics software, RStudio.
- **Open Science support:** Research IT supports Open Science by providing infrastructure, tools, and expertise for data management, open access publishing, and collaboration. This helps promote transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration in research. Skills4EOSC has developed a [minimum viable skillset for Research IT](#) staff in the context of support for EOSC developments ([see 3.7.1 below](#)).
- **Compliance:** Universities are obligated to adhere to legal and ethical standards when managing research data. Research IT ensures compliance with regulations by providing and supporting infrastructures that adhere to these requirements.
- **Collaboration and Networking:** Research IT assists collaboration among university researchers and external partners, for example by research-specific communication networks (e.g. Science DMZ), and facilitating access to shared resources.
- **Grant Applications and Funding:** Researchers often need to demonstrate their technical capabilities when applying for grants. Research IT can collaborate on research proposals by showcasing the university's technological infrastructure and demonstrating that appropriate resources are available within the institution for carrying out the research project.
- **Procurement consultation/advice:** Ability to advise on IT infrastructure/software requirements for research (projects) and support procurement processes.
- **Training:** Research IT often have responsibility for provision of training – formal and informal – to researchers. Examples of training given include software (statistical, storage, visualisation, analytical) introduction, training and development, HPC usage, database management and querying, collaborative tools and platforms, cybersecurity compliance.

2.2 Organisational Integration & Outreach

In addition to the core technical competences detailed above, Research IT plays a crucial role in facilitating cross-institutional engagement, as well as outreach with external stakeholders and research collaborators. These relationships extend beyond central IT services, encompassing the broader research ecosystem, including areas such as Ethics & Integrity, Data Protection & Stewardship, Library Services, and Open Research Support.

A comprehensive understanding of the research lifecycle, along with knowledge of the services, interactions, and compliance requirements at the institutional level, is essential, even where the Research IT function is not directly responsible, i.e., signposting and directing researchers to the appropriate resources.

Research IT may be involved in supporting the development and operations of international Research Infrastructures, including ERICs (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) such as CESSDA, Mariner-I, GUIDE and e-Infrastructures (PRACE). In these cases, as well as the need to support the technology and their operations, Research IT staff may also be involved in international policy developments and infrastructure governance relating to the

implementation and use of RIs. These issues reflect nationally on issues such as AUP (Acceptable Usage Policy) and national funding that Research IT needs to be involved in.

In some cases, research IT may take a leadership role in these international discussions, in other cases they may support a PI with domain specific expertise.

2.3 Research IT as a Training Function

Training provided by Research IT Staff broadly falls into three main delivery methods:

2.3.1 Self-Guided/Independent Resources

- Supplier provided troubleshooting guidelines, manuals and support services (noting that Research IT are often responsible for maintaining these contracts with suppliers)
- Locally produced materials, e.g. recorded webinars, screencasts, written(online) guidance.

In most cases, institutions also provide self-guided supports such as LinkedIn Learning and MS Training Base, Learn. Institutional memberships may also provide access to training resources such as workshops, seminars, e.g. Research Professional.

2.3.2 Formal

While there is no consistent approach for formal training from Research IT for researchers – largely due to the lack of a standard model of Research IT provision in institutions – where there is formal training provided it is usually either:

- Delivered by external service providers as part of a contract, e.g. Elsevier Scopus, SciVAL.
- Delivered by external trainers at a cost, to the institution or via a funded research project.
- Delivered by Research IT staff as part of a general programme of training and specific to certain programmes that are widely used, e.g. NVivo, R, Stata. Generally, such training courses are not-for-credit in the HEI context.
- Notionally there is an understanding, or possibility, that Research IT staff would deliver specific and formal training to research groups as needed, but anecdotally this does not seem to be common practice, and requests from specific projects generally fall into ‘informal and on demand’ below.
- A combination of the above.

There is typically little formal training in any new starter or onboarding process for research staff.

2.3.3 Informal & On Demand

Most of the training provided by Research IT staff to researchers - beyond generalist supports – is delivered informally, often in response to queries, and often on a best-efforts basis, rather than a structured model of researcher support. This ‘training’ can take the form of troubleshooting and problem-solving in addition to answering queries on specific tasks and software. Increasingly these queries relate to HPC.

While most institutions have an IT ticketing system, the specialist nature of Research IT may result in either direct queries to the individual(s), or researchers being ‘lost’ in a ticketing

system designed for general IT queries. Central ticketing works best for Research IT when appropriate signposting is in place within the ticketing system.

A scalable and measurable solution is desirable.

Note that general staff training provided by IT services, e.g. cybersecurity, relevant to researchers but not specifically given by Research IT is considered out of scope here.

3. How to organise Research IT?

3.1 Historical Context

There is no single best-practise example of an organisational structure for Research IT; for most HEIs, the provision of Research IT services generally develops organically based on the resources and history of the institution.

Research related IT services may be provided via institutional units such as IT Services or by the institutional Library; via local units such as permanent departmental staff or staff funded by research projects; or by some combination thereof.

Experience suggests that it is more common for Research IT staff to come from a research background (albeit with technical skills) into this area, rather than for IT staff to move into this specialised area, which may have little application in the private sector.

3.2 Institutional Support Required

In HEIs IT Services units are primarily focussed on the institutional enterprise infrastructure (e.g., student information systems, institutional website) and the institutional Library is primarily focussed on provision of core Library services. However, in many HEIs, IT Services units and Libraries provide research-related IT services, often on an ad hoc, ticketed basis or on a 'good will / best effort' basis, where tasks are assigned to individuals with the necessary skills.

In some cases, a more formal approach has been adopted, with specific percentages of roles or several full-time equivalents (FTE) within IT Services dedicated to this task. However, with the growth of data-driven research, high-performance computing and machine learning and the associated need for significant and compliant research data storage and compute (in-cloud and on-premises), provision of research-related IT services in the absence of dedicated research IT resources is becoming unsustainable.

3.3 Managing Disaggregated Services

Individual departments and research centres often have dedicated staff to run research IT infrastructure. On-premises infrastructure may be hosted in departmental data centres or in institutional data centres. In either case, the infrastructure will be on the institutional network¹ and should be maintained with the knowledge and agreement of the institutional IT Services

¹ It is not likely, or recommended, that individual departments have separate connections to the public internet, as this is likely to bring additional risk to the institution. Therefore, departmental research infrastructure will almost always be on the institutional network

and other relevant stakeholders, e.g. the Data Protection Officer. This will enable locally run research infrastructure to be maintained in accordance with the institutional IT policies.

3.4 On-site Research IT Infrastructure

Provision of on-premises research-related IT infrastructure generally follows the same model as the HEI uses for provision of services: institutional units will use institutional data centres or server rooms, and local services will often use departmental server rooms.

As the demand for research ‘compute and storage’ expands across faculties and research domains, local server rooms and data centres will become less viable for all but the largest schools/departments in terms of size, power supply, cooling and sustainability and additionally in terms of compliance with building regulations. A central function is required.

3.5 In-Cloud Research IT Infrastructure

The hosting and running of research-related IT infrastructure in the public cloud follows similar support patterns to those described above – IT support may be at an institutional or local level. In either case, creation and maintenance of the research environments should be in concert with institutional units relevant to the project, in particular with respect to data protection and cost management.

3.6 Online Information for Researchers

At various stages of the research lifecycle, researchers require information about IT resources available for their research -- at an institutional, national and international level.

In a HEI, online information for researchers regarding available options for research related IT resources should ideally be provided in one location, i.e., a Research IT Services Catalogue. The development and maintenance of this documentation should be a collaborative effort between all units delivering research IT services in the HEI.

If multiple units independently maintain their own online research IT information, the result for researchers will be that information on available infrastructure is difficult to find and often contradictory.

3.7 National and International Infrastructure

Significantly advanced Research IT support services are available internationally, particularly in Denmark, Finland and the Netherlands. However, these are not a suitable starting point for Irish HEIs, given service maturity levels and resourcing limitations.

Provision of research IT services should not be an institutional effort alone. National and international research storage and compute resources should be available to complement institutional resources. This prevents doubling up of resources and increased associated costs. Engagement with these wider infrastructures should be a requirement for any Research IT service, [see Section 5 below](#).

3.7.1 European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

The ongoing development of [EOSC](#) and the requirements around compliance and interoperability with the international federation of systems enabling Open Science, will be core to Research IT and support of research infrastructures.

The [EOSC-EU node](#) is the first step towards the web of FAIR data and the first element of the international federation, with machine actionable APIs where:

- Data providers can make their FAIR data available.
- Service providers (compute, storage, apps) can make their services available.
- Researchers can compose dedicated environments to conduct their research combining:
 - Services: compute, storage, apps
 - Data: from repositories

Stakeholders in Open Science in Ireland, which include Research IT, aim to establish an operational co-ordination unit for Open Research-enabling infrastructure in Ireland, notably through a national EOSC node.

4. Strategy for Resourcing Research IT

A first recommendation would be for HEIs to complete a Research IT maturity assessment [using the RESIN model](#), identifying available skills and services within their institution that will help to inform an appropriate Research IT model.

The Maturity Assessment Model is “*designed to enable institutions to conduct an internal analysis of their research support infrastructure across the different areas of the organisation that have a role to play.*”

The scope of the model centres on assessing the ecosystem, supports and digital infrastructure in place to support research within Higher Education Institutions, namely:

- *what support is required for effective Research IT infrastructure, e.g., funding.*
- *which services are reliant on that infrastructure and services, e.g., research data management.”*

Research IT Support Structure

This area of the activity covers the organisational setup of the function of IT research support. Facets to consider include:

- How is research IT delivered to research groups? Is it centralised or per research centre. If multiple support centres are involved, how do they co-ordinate?
- What level of support is offered: Does it have SLAs or is it offered on a best-efforts basis?
- Is there a service management framework in place?

Function	Level 0	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
How is the research IT service delivery organised within your Institute?	The service is provided on an ad hoc basis and is not repeatable.	Support for research IT is provided by the central IT function alongside institutional level services. Non-targeted Limited services.	Some research groups within an institute avail of IT support which is tailored to their specific subject domain.	All researchers have access to a dedicated research IT function staffed with adequate resources. It may be organised centrally or distributed per department with a central co-ordination oversight function.

Fig 1: Excerpt from RESIN Maturity Assessment Model, [10.5281/zenodo.10061181](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10061181).

The goal is to identify where the HEI currently is within that model, and where the HEI would envision themselves to be in time, thus working to identify the activities that will be required to progress.

Further, an audit of skills and capacity based on the competences listed in [Section 2.1](#). should be undertaken, identifying supports available – formal and informal – as well as gaps in the service.

Responsibility for providing Research IT resources and services should, as far as possible be formally assigned within the HEI and as a corollary, identification of gaps and the source of additional resources to remedy these should be incorporated. Ultimately this work should become part of a Research IT Services Catalogue, as outlined in [Section 3.6](#).

5. Available Shared Research IT Services

There are several resources available at both international and national level to assist the Research IT function at Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) in their support for research and researchers.

At a national level, HEAnet and ICHEC are the key providers of infrastructure and services to support research, and consequently Research IT staff at RPOs.

Examples of these services are detailed in the table below with links for further information:

Service	Description	Provider	More information
Filesender	To securely transfer files between individuals	HEAnet	https://www.heanet.ie/services/hosting/filesender
Brokerage	Assist RPOs in streamlining their ICT procurement processes	HEAnet	https://www.heanet.ie/brokerage
Data centre hosting	Enable RPOs to reduce their operational costs by hosting equipment in fully managed data centres in Dublin	HEAnet	https://www.heanet.ie/services/hosting/data-centre-hosting
Research Institute (RI) development consultancy	Support RPOs/researchers in developing RIs by providing information on what supports are available via HEAnet and its international partners	HEAnet	https://www.heanet.ie/services/research-engagement
HPC infrastructure	Access to HPC infrastructure and related services and expertise including post-graduate education	ICHEC	https://www.ichec.ie/academic/national-hpc
HPC consultancy	Specific needs to be defined by the institution	ICHEC	https://www.ichec.ie/academic/training-education
Research Data Management services	Services to support the research data life cycle, including planning, creation, sharing and preserving	EUDAT	https://eudat.eu/
Training, seminars, Knowledge Bases (KBs)	Resources including technology training, skills, seminars on emerging technologies and new services, etc. The range of topics covered is vast.	HEAnet, ICHEC, GEANT, RESIN	https://www.heanet.ie/workshop-resources https://resin.heanet.ie/index.php/events/previous-events/ https://resin.heanet.ie/index.php/events/ https://e-academy.geant.org/moodle/ https://community.geant.org/infoshares/ https://www.ichec.ie/category/expertise/training-education

Cascade funding	Provide information on access to cascade funding from EU projects. These will typically support the development of research infrastructures, free access to services which would otherwise be charged, technology/service innovation and support for Open Science/FAIR data	RESIN, HEAnet, based on information from partners in EU projects	Past examples: https://eudat.eu/projects/dice https://www.egi.eu/project/egi-ace/ https://www.ocre-project.eu/funding-opportunities/cloud-funding https://eoscfuture.eu/funding-opportunities-commercial-services https://community.geant.org/innovationprogramme/
Open Science	Advancing open research practices. Provide platform for communication, consultation and cooperation among key stakeholders in the research system.	NORF (National Open Research Forum)	https://norf.ie/

At both national and international level, there are resources available to research IT staff in terms of training materials, seminars, Knowledge Bases (KBs) on a range of technologies and skills relevant to research IT.

The below provides an overview of supports available to research IT staff and by whom:

Service	National	European
Data services, e.g., storage, sharing, management	IRLDAT: Shared storage service for active research data	EUDAT - European Common Data Infrastructure
High Performance Computing, tier 0/tier 1	ICHEC - Irish Centre for High-End Computing	PRACE - Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe, replaced by EuroHPC
High Performance Computing, tier 2	Locally provided within institution	
Federated identity management	EduGATE provided by HEAnet	eduGAIN provided by GÉANT
Training and Development resources		GLAD - GÉANT Learning and Development
Infrastructure for Open Science	NORF (subsection)	EOSC – European Open Science Cloud OpenAIRE

6. Training Paths for Research IT

6.1 Contextual Training Paths

As with institutional structures for Research IT, training paths for Research IT professionals will be largely dependent on both the background of the staff member and the needs of their organisation based on the service catalogue. As such, training paths should be looked at largely institutionally – or individually – but be informed by the competences outlined in [Sections 2.1 – 2.3](#). For example, a systems administrator within HPC may require training courses on SLURM/ICHEC training more generally, but this may not be applicable for more mainstream support.

6.2 Professional Engagement

Noting the requirements for networking, outreach and engagement with national and international fora and systems, time allocated to professional networking and development of communities of practices should be considered a required activity. For example, at international level, there are recurring EU funded projects that provide cascade funding for the development of Research Infrastructures and the advancement of Open Science.

These are key activities for research IT staff, however being aware of these cascade funding opportunities is challenging. The ‘National Forum for Research Services and Infrastructure’ (RESIN) addresses this challenge by advertising such opportunities to its members. It provides informal training and networking opportunities through its [‘InfoShares’ series](#). It is therefore recommended that research IT functions join the RESIN group to stay up to date with initiatives and resources to support research.

Further, there is an opportunity to develop a community moderated ‘live’ catalogue of training materials undertaken and recommended by Research IT staff as a community support exercise via RESIN.

As part of its Digital Research Infrastructure Programme, the UKRI have recognised the need for skills support and development for Research IT Professionals, and have made [‘People, Culture & Skills’](#) a focus of the programme, implementing training channels and award systems. A similar approach should be developed nationally.

6.3 Challenges

1. As described above, Research IT staff come to the role(s) through a variety of channels, and different institutions have differing requirements. Thus, a defined training path for all staff is not possible, and local approaches are needed – [informed by a skills analysis](#).
2. Many Research IT professionals are employed on temporary contracts, effectively as researchers. Needs are specific to projects, and temporary contracts make incremental development challenging for an organisation.
3. Research IT professionals working as researchers may wish to (or be required to) complete their own research – as funders will not fund IT support staff -, limiting the development of Research IT services outside of the conducting of research.
4. A lack of clear career path for Research IT staff. Progression is limited by any/all of the following:

- Temporary Contracts.
- Lack of managerial grades for IT more generally in current agreed frameworks.
- Niche area that does not necessarily align with 'central IT' for progressional movement; can be siloed.

7. Conclusion

This paper provides a comprehensive exploration of Research IT as a vital function within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), emphasising its critical role in advancing research capabilities, fostering collaboration, and ensuring compliance with ethical and legal standards. By examining the current landscape in Ireland, the document underscores the unique challenges and opportunities inherent to the development and management of Research IT.

The outlined competences, organisational models, and strategic recommendations aim to serve as a foundation for HEIs to evaluate and enhance their Research IT services. This work advocates for a tailored approach, acknowledging the diverse needs of institutions and their research communities, while also promoting collaboration at national and international levels to leverage shared resources effectively.

The adoption of maturity assessment models like RESIN and targeted training paths can aid institutions in bridging gaps, fostering innovation, and nurturing the specialised skills necessary for this domain. As the field continues to evolve, this document serves as an initial starting point to guide HEIs toward sustainable and effective Research IT solutions, with the ultimate goal of strengthening the infrastructure and support systems that underpin research excellence.